

Mathematical Analysis of Sensitive Parameters on the Dynamical Transmission of Ebola-Malaria Co-infections

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Abstract-Malaria is an important mimic or co-infection in potential Ebola virus disease patients. In this work, a mathematical model was developed to incorporate the biological features of both Ebola virus and malaria disease. The analysis showed that the model is well-posed, the disease free equilibria for the model was obtained and basic reproduction number $R_{EM} = 0.8607599873$ of the Ebola-malaria co-infection model is calculated. The model was analyzed for stability and it established that the disease free equilibrium of co-infections model were locally and globally asymptotically stable whenever the basic reproduction number is less than unity or endemic otherwise. Sensitivity analysis on the basic reproduction number reveal the most sensitive index value and the graph in figure6 shows that by eliminating the co-infection contact rate of Ebola- malaria disease in the population in other to control Ebola-malaria co-infection.

Keywords: Ebola-malaria co-infection, model description, basic reproduction number and sensitivity analysis.

I. Introduction

Ebola virus and Malaria co-infection is common especially in the developing countries where malaria is already endemic. Malaria caused about 438, 000 deaths in 2015 alone, and while Ebola virus claims 11, 310 people [16]. The literature and development of mathematical epidemiology is well documented and can be found in [9]. Important results on the transmission dynamics of typhoid only have been revealed in the last decade, for instance see [20], in his paper, a mathematical model is formulated using system of differential equations to understand the co-dynamics of two diseases - HIV/AIDS and Malaria. The entire human population (age 16-45 years) is divided into six compartments and mosquito population into two. The model is analyzed and steady state conditions are derived. It is shown that the disease free equilibrium is stable if the basic reproduction number, R , is less than unity. Sensitivity analysis and simulation results prove that malaria makes people move faster from HIV to AIDS class and reduce their life span.

[1] worked on sensitivity analysis of the dynamical Spread of Ebola virus disease, deterministic model was studied to gain insight into the dynamical spread of Ebola virus disease, and it concludes that the rate of public enlightenment and availability of isolation centers can reduce the spread of Ebola virus disease. Increment in the values of public enlightenment and isolation centers reduced the basic reproduction number since the spread of disease is dependent on the value of. Therefore effort that targets the use of condom as a control measure should be encouraged. [21

proposed and investigated a deterministic model for the co-infection of HIV and malaria in a community.

[22] examined a mathematical model that covers the dynamics of Cholera transmission to study the influence of public health educational campaigns, vaccination and treatment in controlling the disease. In this paper we use clinical malaria data from Ghana Health Service at WHO Website to develop a mathematical model to investigate and understand the disease transmission dynamics in Ghana taking both host and vector populations into account [3] used a SEIR model to explain the 2014 West African Ebola virus epidemic with an assumption that the epidemic started with a single infected case. [4,1] formulate a mathematical modeling and optimal control of Ebola virus disease, a nonlinear mathematical model was developed and analyzed to study the dynamics of Ebola virus (EVD) and the effects of some control strategies. Numerical simulation was carried out and the results obtained indicate that a combination of all three control parameters is highly effective in containing the spread of the virus.

[1,19] formulated a susceptible infected-recovered-death model to study the spread of Ebola virus disease transmission in Sub-Saharan African countries. It was assumed that recovered individuals lost immunity and become susceptible again with natural death in susceptible infected recovered (SIR) compartments. [1] formulate a mathematical analysis of effects of isolation on Ebola transmission dynamics, it shows that if the detection rate of infected undetected individuals is sufficiently large, then the isolation technique can lead to elimination of Ebola in the population. Also if the isolation rate of exposed and infected individuals are high and the effective contact rate ranges between (0.113-0.9), then the disease can be eradicated in the community.

To the best of my knowledge, Ebola virus and malaria Co-infection model has not been done by any researcher or been published. It is in this regard that a mathematical model for the Co-infection Ebola-Malaria is proposed to access the effect of Ebola in the Malaria endemic region. Therefore, this study is imperative for the researcher and the public health officials because the early symptoms of both diseases sometimes confuse the medical practitioners and the victims as well.

II. Model description and Formulation

A mathematical model is formulated to consider the dynamics spread of Ebola–Malaria co-infection transmission. The human population is divided into eleven classes, susceptible individuals $S_H(t)$, Ebola virus disease latently infected individuals $L_E(t)$, Ebola virus disease infected undetected Individuals $I_U(t)$, infected detected Ebola virus disease individuals $I_D(t)$, individuals under treatment for Ebola virus disease $I_T(t)$, individuals isolated for Ebola virus disease J , individuals exposed to malaria disease only $E_M(t)$, individuals infected with malaria $I_M(t)$, individuals that recovered from malaria $R_M(t)$, Ebola virus disease exposed malaria Individuals $E_{EM}(t)$, active or infected Ebola - malaria individuals $I_{EM}(t)$. Therefore the total population of human denoted by;

$$N_H(t) = S_H(t) + L_E(t) + I_U(t) + I_D(t) + I_T(t) + J(t) + E_M(t) + I_M(t) + R_M(t) + E_{EM}(t) + I_{EM}(t) \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the total vector (mosquito) population is sub-divided into susceptible mosquitoes $S_v(t)$, exposed mosquitoes $E_v(t)$ and the infected mosquitoes $I_v(t)$ so that the total population of mosquitoes denoted by;

$$N_v(t) = S_v(t) + E_v(t) + I_v(t) \quad (2)$$

It is assumed that susceptible humans are generated into the population at the constant rate π_H and acquire Ebola virus diseases, malaria and Ebola –Malaria disease infection at a rate of λ_E , λ_M and λ_{EM} . The population increases by fraction of recovered individuals who loss immunity (at a rate ϕ_1) as well as the fraction of isolated individual who move to susceptible after test negative of Ebola virus disease infection but natural death occurs in all human sub- population (at the rate μ), which decreases the population. The force of infection associated with Ebola virus disease, denoted by,

$$\lambda_E = \beta_E \left(\frac{I_U + \eta_D I_D + \eta_T I_T + \eta_J J}{N_H} \right) \quad (3)$$

In (3) β_E represents the effective contact rate (contact result in Ebola infection), η_D is a modification parameter comparing the individual transmissibility of detected infected individuals in relationship to latently infected. Since detected individuals are under treatment and isolation, it is intuitive to assume that $\eta_D \leq 1$. Similarly η_T and η_J are modification parameters comparing the transmissibility of infected individuals in the treated class and isolated class respectively.

Thus, the rate of change of susceptible population is given by;

$$\frac{dS_H}{dt} = \pi_H - \lambda_E S_H - \lambda_M S_H - \lambda_{EM} S_H - \mu S_H + \phi_1 R_M + \alpha \theta I \quad (4)$$

A fraction of ε_1 new infected individuals with low immunity move to the latent class (L_E), while the remaining fraction $(1-\varepsilon_1)$ move to infected undetected class (fast progressor) I_U . The population of latently infected class is further increased by the individuals who are successfully treated (at the rate ϕ_2), fraction of isolated individual that move to latent class without being certified Ebola free at the rate $(1-\rho)\theta$ and by fraction of individuals who are treated for Ebola infectious - malaria (at a rate $(1-\rho)\phi_3$), since malaria is curable. The population decreases by progression to Ebola – detected class (at rate K_E), natural death (at the rate μ) and isolation (at the rate σ_1).

Hence,

$$\frac{dL_E}{dt} = \varepsilon_1 \lambda_E S_H - (\kappa_E + \sigma_1 + \mu) L_E + \phi_2 I_T + (1 - \alpha) \theta J - (1 - \rho) \phi_3 I_{EM} \quad (5)$$

The population of undetected Ebola infected individual is increased by fraction of the newly infected individuals with low immunity (at the rate ε_1) and those that develop symptoms by the latently infected individuals (at the rate $\omega_1 \kappa_E$), where ω_1 is the fraction of latently infected individuals who are not detected ($\omega_1 \kappa_E$). Also, it decreases by the detection of the infection (at the rate γ_{UE}), natural death (at the μ) and disease induced death (at a rate δ_{UE}).

Thus;

$$\frac{dI_U}{dt} = (1 - \varepsilon_1) \lambda_E S_H + \omega_1 \kappa_E L_E - (\gamma_{UE} + \mu + \delta_{UE}) I_U \quad (6)$$

The detected population is increased by a fraction latently infected individuals who are detected upon showing symptoms (at the rate $(1 - \omega_1) \kappa_E$). Also, the population increases due to Ebola exposed malaria individuals that are treated (at the rate τ_4), and by the detection rate of undetected individuals (at the rate γ_{UE}). The population is decreased by treatment (at the rate τ_1), isolation (at the rate σ_2), natural death (at the rate μ) and disease induced death (at a rate δ_{DE}). Hence;

$$\frac{dI_D}{dt} = (1 - \omega_1) \kappa_E L_E - (\tau_1 + \mu + \delta_{DE} + \sigma_2) I_D + \gamma_{UE} I_U + \tau_4 E_{EM} \quad (7)$$

The population of treated class increases by the treatment of detected individuals (at the rate τ_1). Since, Ebola can be cure by early detected and treatment, individuals move to latently infected class (at the rate ϕ_2). Also, the population also decreases by natural death (at the rate μ).

Then,

$$\frac{dI_T}{dt} = \tau_1 I_D - (\phi_2 + \mu) I_T \quad (8)$$

The population of the isolated individual increases by the isolation of latently infected individuals and detected individuals (at the rate σ_1 and σ_2 respectively) and decreases by natural death (at the rate μ) and disease induced death (at the rate δ_j). This gives,

$$\frac{dJ}{dt} = \sigma_1 L_E + \sigma_2 I_D - (\mu + \delta_j) J - \theta J \quad (9)$$

Invariably, human acquires malaria infection following effective contact with infected mosquitoes at a rate λ_M , given by

$$\lambda_M = \frac{\beta_M a I_V}{N_V} \quad (10)$$

Where β_M is the transmission probability from mosquito to human provided that there is a contact between the human and the mosquito and "a" is the number of mosquito bites that one person has per unit time.

A fraction ϵ_2 of new infected individuals with low immunity move to the exposed class (E_M) and the remaining fraction $(1-\epsilon_2)$ move to the infected class (I_M). The exposed class population increases by those that are treated (at the rate $\rho\phi_3$). The exposed class decreases by progression to infected individuals (at the rate κ_M), those that are treated (at the rate τ_2), natural death (at the rate μ).

Thus;

$$\frac{dE_M}{dt} = \epsilon_2 \lambda_M S_M - (\kappa_M + \mu) E_M - \tau_2 E_M + \rho\phi_3 I_{EM} \quad (11)$$

The population of individual infected with malaria is generated by a fraction of the new infected individuals with low immunity (at the rate $1-\epsilon_2$) and progression to infected individuals from the exposed class. The population decreases by treatment of the infected individuals (at the rate τ_3), those who are successfully treated and recovered (at the rate r), natural death (at the rate μ) and disease induced death (at the rate δ_{IM}).

Therefore,

$$\frac{dI_M}{dt} = (1-\epsilon_2) \lambda_M S_H + \kappa_M E_M - (\tau_3 + r + \delta_{IM} + \mu) I_M \quad (12)$$

The recovered population is generated by treatment (at the rate τ_2 and τ_3) of the exposed and infected class respectively and those who are successfully treated and recovered (at the rate r). There is decreased in the population due to natural death (at the rate μ) and those that loss immunity (at the rate ϕ_1). Hence;

$$\frac{dR_M}{dt} = \tau_2 E_M + \tau_3 I_M + r I_M - (\phi_1 + \mu) R_M \quad (13)$$

Furthermore, the force of infection associated with Ebola virus – malaria co-infection is denoted

$$\lambda_{EM} = \beta_{EM} \frac{(E_{EM} + \eta_{EM} I_{EM})}{N_H}$$

by; (14)

where β_{EM} is the effective contact rate and η_{EM} is the modification parameter respectively.

The population of Ebola virus exposed malaria is generated by a fraction ε_3 of newly infected individuals with low immunity who move to Ebola virus exposed malaria class while the remaining fraction move to the active Ebola-malaria class. The population decreases due to progression to active Ebola - malaria (at the rate κ_{EM}), treatment of the population (at the rate τ_4), natural death (at the rate μ) and death due to the disease (at the rate δ_{EM}). Therefore;

$$\frac{dE_{EM}}{dt} = \varepsilon_3 \lambda_{EM} S_H - (\kappa_{EM} + \delta_{EM} + \mu) E_{EM} - \tau_4 E_{EM}$$
(15)

Active Ebola virus- malaria class contains the remaining fraction $1 - \varepsilon_3$ of newly infected individuals with low immunity (at the rate $1 - \varepsilon_3$) and those that progresses from Ebola exposed malaria class (at the rate κ_{EM}). The class decreases by those that are successfully treated (at the rate ϕ_3), natural death (at the rate μ) and death due to disease (at the rate δ_{EM}). Hence

$$\frac{dI_{EM}}{dt} = (1 - \varepsilon_3) \lambda_{EM} S_H + \kappa_{EM} E_{EM} - (\phi_3 + \delta_{EM} + \mu) I_{EM}$$
(16)

Susceptible vectors S_V are generated at a constant (recruitment rate π_V) and acquire malaria infection following effective contacts with humans infected with malaria at a rate λ_v , where the force of infection λ_v is given by;

$$\lambda_v = \frac{\beta_M b (I_M + \eta_1 E_{EM} + \eta_2 I_{EM})}{N_H}$$
(17)

Where η_1 and η_2 are the modification parameter b is the number of human bites one mosquito has per unit time, β_M is the transmission probability from human to mosquito. Newly infected mosquitoes move to exposed class and they are assumed to suffer death (at a rate μ_V).

Hence;

$$\frac{dS_V}{dt} = \pi_V - \lambda_V S_V - \mu_V S_V \quad (18)$$

The exposed mosquitoes consist of newly infected mosquitoes and their population diminishes by progression into infected class (at the rate σ_V) and death of the mosquitoes (at the rate μ_V). Therefore;

$$\frac{dE_V}{dt} = \lambda_V S_V - (\sigma_V + \mu_V) E_V \quad (19)$$

The infected mosquitoes have those that progress from exposed class and diminish by the death of the mosquitoes (at the rate μ_V)

Hence,

$$\frac{dI_V}{dt} = \sigma_V E_V - \mu_V I_V \quad (20)$$

Putting all the above assumptions together obtain the following system of differential equations.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS_H}{dt} &= \pi_H - \lambda_E S_H - \lambda_M S_H - \lambda_{EM} S_H - \mu S_H + \phi_1 R_M + \alpha \theta J \\ \frac{dL_E}{dt} &= \varepsilon_1 \lambda_E S_H - (\kappa_E + \sigma_1 + \mu) L_E + \phi_2 I_T + (1 - \alpha) \theta J - (1 - \rho) \phi_3 I_{EM} \\ \frac{dI_U}{dt} &= (1 - \varepsilon_1) \lambda_E S_H + \omega_1 \kappa_E L_E - (\gamma_{UE} + \mu + \delta_{UE}) I_U \\ \frac{dI_D}{dt} &= (1 - \omega_1) \kappa_E L_E - (\tau_1 + \mu + \delta_{DE} + \sigma_2) I_D + \gamma_{UE} I_U + \tau_4 E_{EM} \\ \frac{dI_T}{dt} &= \tau_1 I_D - (\phi_2 + \mu) I_T \\ \frac{dJ}{dt} &= \sigma_1 L_E + \sigma_2 I_D - (\mu + \delta_j) J - \theta J \\ \frac{dE_M}{dt} &= \varepsilon_2 \lambda_M S_H - (\kappa_M + \mu) E_M - \tau_2 E_M + \rho \phi_3 I_{EM} \\ \frac{dI_M}{dt} &= (1 - \varepsilon_2) \lambda_M S_H + \kappa_M E_M - (\tau_3 + r + \delta_{IM} + \mu) I_M \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{dR_M}{dt} = \tau_2 E_M + \tau_3 I_M + r I_M - (\phi_1 + \mu) R_M$$

$$\frac{dE_{EM}}{dt} = \varepsilon_3 \lambda_{EM} S_H - (\kappa_{EM} + \delta_{IEM} + \mu) E_{EM} - \tau_4 E_{EM}$$

$$\frac{dI_{EM}}{dt} = (1 - \varepsilon_3) \lambda_{EM} S_H + \kappa_{EM} E_{EM} - (\phi_3 + \delta_{IEM} + \mu) I_{EM}$$

$$\frac{dS_V}{dt} = \pi_V - \lambda_V S_V - \mu_V S_V$$

$$\frac{dE_V}{dt} = \lambda_V S_V - (\sigma_V + \mu_V) E_V$$

$$\frac{dI_V}{dt} = \sigma_V E_V - \mu_V I_V$$

Where

$$\lambda_E = \beta_E \left(\frac{I_U + \eta_D I_D + \eta_T I_T + \eta_J J}{N_H} \right), \quad \lambda_{EM} = \beta_{EM} \frac{(E_{EM} + \eta_{EM} I_{EM})}{N_H}, \quad \lambda_M = \frac{\beta_M b I_V}{N_V},$$

$$\lambda_V = \frac{\beta_V b (I_M + \eta_1 E_{EM} + \eta_2 I_{EM})}{N_H}$$

Table 1: Definitions of parameters and variables used in the model formulation

PARAMETERS/ VARIABLES	DEFINITIONS
S_H	Susceptible individuals
L_E	Ebola virus latently infected individuals
I_U	Undetected Ebola virus individuals
I_D	Detected Ebola virus individual
I_T	Ebola virus treated individuals
J	Isolated Ebola virus disease individuals
E_M	Malaria exposed individuals
I_M	Malaria infected individuals
R_M	Malaria recovered individuals

L_{EM}	Ebola virus exposed malaria individuals
I_{EM}	Ebola virus-malaria infected individuals
S_V	Susceptible vectors (mosquitoes)
E_V	Exposed vectors (mosquitoes)
I_V	Infected vectors (mosquitoes)
π_H, π_V	Recruitment rate of human and vectors respectively
$\lambda_M, \lambda_E, \lambda_{EM}$	Forces of infection in Malaria, Ebola virus and Ebola - malaria individuals
μ	Human death rate
μ_V	vectors (mosquitoes) death rate
$\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \tau_4$	Treatment rate for malaria exposed, malaria infected, Ebola virus detected and Ebola virus exposed malaria individuals
$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$	Fraction of individuals with low immunity, Infected with Ebola virus, malaria and Ebola virus-malaria co-infection
γ_{UE}	Detection rate for undetected Ebola virus disease
δ_{EM}, δ_{IM}	Malaria induced death rate for classes E_M, I_M
$\delta_{UE}, \delta_{DE}, \delta_j, \delta_{EM}, \delta_{IEM}$	EVD induced death rate for classes I_U, I_D, J, E_{EM} and I_{EM} respectively
$\kappa_E, \kappa_M, \kappa_{EM}$	Progression rate for Ebola virus, malaria and Ebola virus-malaria
σ_1, σ_2	Isolation rate for classes L_H and I_D respectively
β_E, β_{EM}	Effective contact rate for Ebola virus and Ebola virus-malaria respectively

β_M, β_V	Transmission probability from mosquito to human and human to mosquito respectively
ω_1	Fraction of latently infected class that moves to Ebola virus undetected class
σ_V	Progression rate of vectors (mosquitoes)
ρ	Fraction of active Ebola virus-malaria that is treated which moves to malaria exposed class
ϕ_2	Progression rate Ebola virus treated class to latent class
ϕ_3	Progression rate of active Ebola virus-malaria individual after treatment
r	Recovery rate of malaria
b	Number of mosquito bites per unit time
λ_M, λ_V	Force of infection from mosquito to human and from human to mosquito respectively
ϕ	Rate of loss of immunity

A. Boundedness solutions of the model

For the system (21) to be epidemiologically meaningful, it is important to prove that all solutions with non-negative initial data will remain non-negative i.e. $t \geq 0$

Theorem1 If

$S_H(0), L_E(0), I_U(0), I_D(0), I_T(0), J(0), E_M(0), I_M(0), E_{EM}(0), I_{EM}(0), R_M(0), S_V(0), E_V(0), I_V(0)$ be non-negative, then the solutions

$S_H, L_E, I_U, I_D, I_T, J, E_M, I_M, E_{EM}, I_{EM}, R_M, S_V, E_V$ and I_V for all $t > 0$

Proof:

Consider the biologically- feasible region $\Omega = \Omega_H \times \Omega_V \subset \mathfrak{R}_+^{14}$, with

$$\Omega_H = \left\{ (S_H, L_E, I_U, I_D, I_T, J, E_M, I_M, E_{EM}, I_{EM}, R_M) \in \mathfrak{R}_+^{11} : N_H \leq \frac{\pi_H}{\mu} \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$\Omega_V = \left\{ (S_V, E_V, I_V) \in \mathfrak{R}_+^3 : N_V \leq \frac{\pi_V}{\mu_V} \right\} \text{ is positively invariant.}$$

From this theorem, this can be conclude that it is sufficient to consider the dynamics of (21) in Ω . In this region, the model can be considered as being epidemiologically well-posed [24]

The total human population N_H is calculated as:

$$N_H = S_H + L_E + I_U + I_D + I_T + J + E_M + I_M + E_{EM} + I_{EM} + R_M$$

Therefore upon simplifications obtain the following

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_H}{dt} = & \pi_H - \mu(S_H + L_E + I_U + I_D + I_T + J + E_M + I_M + E_{EM} + I_{EM} + R_M) \\ & - (\delta_{UE} I_U + \delta_{DE} I_D + \delta_J J + \delta_{IM} I_M + \delta_{EM} E_{EM} + \delta_{IEM} I_{EM}) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

If there is no death from Ebola and malaria infections, equation (3.76) become;

$$\frac{dN_H}{dt} \leq \pi_H - \mu N_H \quad (23)$$

After, solving equation (23) and evaluating it as time tends to infinity, obtain;

$$N_H(t) \leq N_H(0)e^{-\mu t} + \frac{\pi_H}{\mu} (1 - e^{-\mu t}) \quad (24)$$

Where $N_H(0)$ represents the value of total population of human evaluated at the initial values of the respective variables.

Similarly, the rate of change of the total population of vectors (mosquitoes) N_V is calculated as:

$$N_V = S_V + E_V + I_V$$

Thus obtain

$$\frac{dN_V}{dt} = \pi_V - \mu_V (S_V + E_V + I_V) \quad (25)$$

$$\text{Then, } \frac{dN_V}{dt} \leq \pi_V - \mu_V N_V \quad (26)$$

After, solving equation (3.80) and evaluating it as time tends to infinity, obtain;

$$N_V(t) \leq N_V(0)e^{-\mu_V t} + \frac{\pi_V}{\mu_V} (1 - e^{-\mu_V t}) \quad (27)$$

Where $N_V(0)$ represents the value of total population of the vectors (mosquitoes) evaluated at the initial values of the respective variables.

Thus as $t \rightarrow \infty$, equations (24) and (27) become;

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N_H(t) \leq \frac{\pi_H}{\mu} \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} N_V(t) \leq \frac{\pi_V}{\mu_V}$$

$$\text{If } N_H(0) \leq \frac{\pi_H}{\mu} \quad \text{and} \quad N_V(0) \leq \frac{\pi_V}{\mu_V}$$

Therefore, all the solution set of (21) is bounded in Ω .

B. Equilibrium analysis of the model

The disease free equilibrium of equation (21) is obtained by equating all equations of the model to zero and then set $L_E = I_U = I_D = I_T = J = E_M = I_M = R_M = E_{EM} = I_{EM} = E_V = I_V = 0$. Then

$$\text{obtain: } E_0 = \left(\frac{\pi_H}{\mu}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\pi_V}{\mu_V}, 0, 0 \right)$$

C. The basic reproductive number of model.

Follow the principle of next generation matrix, from the above model equation, the non-negative matrix F (new infection terms) and the non-singular matrix V (i.e other transferring terms) can be partition as follow;

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} F_1 & F_2 \\ F_3 & F_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad V = \begin{bmatrix} V_1 & V_2 \\ V_3 & V_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4 and V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4 are 6x6 matrices. ;

Therefore, from the model equation the non-negative matrices F₁ to F₄ (new infection term rate) are as follows;

$$F_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \varepsilon_1 \beta_E & \varepsilon_1 \beta_E \eta_D & \varepsilon_1 \beta_E \eta_T & \varepsilon_1 \beta_E \eta_J & 0 \\ 0 & (1 - \varepsilon_1) \beta_E & (1 - \varepsilon_1) \beta_E \eta_D & (1 - \varepsilon_1) \beta_E \eta_T & (1 - \varepsilon_1) \beta_E \eta_J & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$F_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\varepsilon_2 \beta_M b \pi_H \mu_V}{\mu \pi_V} \end{pmatrix} \quad F_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$F_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{(1-\varepsilon_2)\beta_M b \pi_H \mu_V}{\mu \pi_V} \\ 0 & \varepsilon_3 \beta_{EM} & \varepsilon_3 \beta_{EM} \eta_{EM} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (1-\varepsilon_3)\beta_{EM} & (1-\varepsilon_3)\beta_{EM} \eta_{EM} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Other transferring terms V_1 to V_4 are given as follows.

$$V_1 = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_2 & -a_2 & 0 \\ -\omega_1 \kappa_H & a_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -a_5 & -\gamma_{UE} & a_6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\tau_1 & a_7 & 0 & 0 \\ -\sigma_1 & 0 & -\sigma_2 & 0 & a_8 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_9 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$V_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -a_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\tau_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\rho \phi_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\kappa_M \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\tau_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad V_4 = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\kappa_{EM} & b_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -b_4 & 0 & 0 & b_5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b_6 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sigma_V & \mu_V \end{bmatrix}$$

Where

$$a_1 = \kappa_E + \mu + \sigma_1, a_2 = (1 - \alpha)\theta, a_3 = (1 - \rho)\phi_3, a_4 = \gamma_{UE} + \mu + \delta_{UE}, a_5 = (1 - \omega_1)\kappa_E,$$

$$a_6 = \tau_1 + \mu + \delta_{DE} + \sigma_2, a_7 = \phi_2 + \mu, a_8 = \mu + \delta_j + \theta, a_9 = \kappa_M + \mu + \tau_2, b_1 = \tau_3 + r + \delta_{IM} + \mu,$$

$$b_2 = \kappa_{EM} + \mu + \delta_{IEM} + \tau_4, b_3 = \phi_3 + \delta_{IEM} + \mu, b_4 = \tau_3 + r, b_5 = \phi_1 + \mu, b_6 = \sigma_V + \mu_V$$

From the above matrix, V_2 and V_3 are singular matrices, then $(F_1V_1^{-1})$ and $(F_4V_4^{-1})$ will be considered for the calculation of the reproduction number.

Therefore, the reproduction number R_1 of the matrix F_1V_1 is:

$$R_1 = \beta_E \frac{\left(\begin{array}{l} \varepsilon_1 a_1 a_7 a_8 \eta_D \gamma_{UE} + \varepsilon_1 a_1 a_7 a_8 \eta_J \gamma_{UE} \tau_1 - \varepsilon_1 a_2 a_7 \eta_D \gamma_{UE} \sigma_1 - \varepsilon_1 a_2 \eta_T \gamma_{UE} \sigma_1 \tau_1 + \varepsilon_1 \eta_J \gamma_{UE} \phi_2 \sigma_1 \tau_1 \\ - a_4 a_5 a_7 a_8 \varepsilon_1 \eta_D - a_4 a_5 a_7 \varepsilon_1 \eta_J \sigma_2 - a_4 a_5 a_8 \varepsilon_1 \eta_T \tau_1 - a_4 a_6 a_7 \varepsilon_1 \eta_J \sigma_1 - a_1 a_7 a_8 \eta_D \gamma_{UE} - a_1 a_7 \eta_J \\ \gamma_{UE} \sigma_2 - a_1 a_8 \eta_T \gamma_{UE} \tau_1 + a_2 a_7 \eta_D \gamma_{UE} \sigma_1 + a_2 \eta_T \gamma_{UE} \sigma_1 \tau_1 - \eta_J \gamma_{UE} \phi_2 \sigma_1 \tau_1 + \varepsilon_1 a_1 a_6 a_7 a_8 - \varepsilon_1 a_2 \\ a_5 a_7 \sigma_2 - \varepsilon_1 a_2 a_6 a_7 \sigma_1 - \varepsilon_1 a_5 a_8 \phi_2 \tau_1 - a_1 a_6 a_7 a_8 + a_2 a_5 a_7 \sigma_2 + a_2 a_5 a_7 \sigma_1 + a_5 a_8 \phi_2 \tau_1 - \varepsilon_1 \omega_1 \\ \kappa_E a_6 a_7 a_8 - \varepsilon_1 a_7 a_8 \eta_D \gamma_{UE} \kappa_E \omega_1 - \varepsilon_1 a_7 \eta_J \gamma_{UE} \kappa_E \omega_1 \sigma_2 - \varepsilon_1 a_8 \eta_T \gamma_{UE} \kappa_E \omega_1 \tau_1 \end{array} \right)}{a_2 a_7 \gamma_{UE} \kappa_E \omega_1 \sigma_2 + a_8 \gamma_{UE} \kappa_E \omega_1 \phi_2 \tau_1 - a_1 a_4 a_6 a_7 a_8 + a_2 a_4 a_5 a_7 \sigma_2 + a_2 a_4 a_6 a_7 \sigma_1 + a_4 a_5 a_8 \phi_2 \tau_1}$$

The associated reproduction number R_4 for $F_4V_4^{-1}$ given by $\rho(F_4V_4^{-1})$, where ρ is the spectral radius of the dominant eigenvalue of the next generation matrix $(F_4V_4^{-1})$ is:

$$R_4 = \frac{\beta_{EM} ((\phi_3 + \delta_{IEM} + \mu)\varepsilon_3 + (\kappa_{EM} + \mu + \delta_{IEM} + \tau_4)\eta_{EM} + \varepsilon_3 \eta_{EM} \kappa_{EM} - \varepsilon_3 \eta_{EM} (\kappa_{EM} + \mu + \delta_{IEM} + \tau_4))}{(\kappa_{EM} + \mu + \delta_{IEM} + \tau_4)(\phi_3 + \delta_{IEM} + \mu)}$$

So, that the basic reproduction number of the Ebola- malaria co-infection model is denoted by $R_{0(EM)} = \max\{R_1, R_4\}$.

III. Sensitivity analysis of the model

Sensitivity analysis was carried out to determine the model robustness to parameter values. This helps to identify the parameters that have a high impact on the reproductive number R_{EM} . Moreover, sensitivity indices helps in developing efficient and effective intervention strategies in the control of Ebola-malaria co-infection in the community.

This was calculated using normalized forward sensitivity method, which is defined as the ratio of

$$Z_P^{R_M} = \frac{\partial R_{EM}}{\partial P} \times \frac{P}{R_{EM}}$$

the relative change in R_{EM} to the relative change in the parameter ‘‘P’’:

Table 2: Sensitivity values on the basic reproduction number R_{EM} of Ebola-malaria Co-infection model

Parameters	Sensitivity indices
β_{EM}	1.000000000

ϵ_3	0.9907058877
ϕ_3	0.5720364764
μ	0.4145191860
δ_{EM}	0.02901634301
η_{EM}	0.01119409061
κ_{EM}	0.004653570032
τ_4	0.0002042987416

IV. Numerical simulation result

The analytical results of this study are illustrated by carrying out numerical simulations of the models using parameter values in table 3.5 with initial values $S_H(0) = 12000$, $L_E(0) = 2000$, $I_U(0) = 200$, $I_D(0) = 300$, $I_T(0) = 350$, $J(0) = 180$, $E_{EM}(0) = 700$, $I_{EM}(0) = 100$, $E_M(0) = 2000$, $I_M(0) = 9000$, $R_M(0) = 7500$, $S_V(0) = 900$, $E_V(0) = 700$, $I_V(0) = 500$ as shown in table (3.5). The simulations are carried out with the help of Maple 17 software and the results are given below

Table 3: Parameters values used for the numerical simulation

Parameters	Values	Sources
δ_{IM}	0.05	Smith &Hove-Musekwa (2008)
β_{EM}	0.8	Estimated
κ_{EM}	0.093	Estimated
κ_M	0.071	[26]
β_M	0.03	[23]
ϵ_3	0.69	Estimated
ϵ_2	0.6	Estimated
τ_4	0.0069	[13]

τ_3	0.0013	[13]
τ_2	0.0018	Estimated
π_V	400	Estimated
π_H	1800	Estimated
μ	0.2	Estimated
μ_V	0.05	[25,26]
τ_1	0.3143	Flahault <i>et al.</i> , (2005)
ε_1	0.92	Flahault <i>et al.</i> , (2005)
γ_{UE}	0.2	Estimated
δ_{EM}	0.093	[21]
κ_E	0.2	[1]
σ_2	0.6	[1]
σ_1	0.712	[1]
β_E	0.8	Estimated
β_V	0.09	[7]
ω_1	0.2	[1]
σ_V	0.1	[10]
ϕ_2	0.02	[1]
ϕ_3	0.28	[13]
r	0.02	[2]
b	0.4	[11]
θ	0.8	[1]

δ_{UE}	0.01	Estimated
δ_{DE}	0.008	Estimated
δ_j	0.06	Estimated
δ_{IEM}	0.014	[6]
$\eta_T, \eta_D, \eta_J,$ η_{EM}	0.01	Estimated

Figure1: Graph showing disease free equilibrium point at different time

Figure 2: Shows the global stability of endemic point at different time

Figure 3: Chart of the sensitivity indices on the basic reproduction number

Figure 4: Behavior of total population with initial value at different time

Figure 5: Graph of increasing the most positive sensitive value which is Ebola-malaria contact rate on total population at different time

Figure 6: Graph of eliminating the most positive sensitive value which is Ebola-malaria contact rate on total population at different time

V. Discussion of results

Figure 1 shows the disease free equilibrium point of Ebola- malaria co-infection, as it shows that there is always susceptible in the population while infected individual tend to zero. Also, figure 2 shows the global stability of endemic that indicate that whatever the initial values the system will converge to the same point as time goes on. In figure 4 depicts the behavior of Ebola- malaria co-infection model with initial values, changes in the fourteen state variables of the co-infection model displaying the dynamics with different time of susceptible, Ebola latently, infected undetected, infected detected, infected treated, isolated, exposed malaria human, infected malaria human, Ebola-malaria exposed, Ebola-malaria infected, susceptible vector, exposed vector and infected vector population.

In figure 5, susceptible population decreases between zero to nine days when contact rate increases while susceptible vector increases and the co-infection trajectories increase. Also, dynamics of their trajectories remain the same. As it shows in figure 6, when contact rate was eliminated on

entire co-infection model susceptible population increases to the peak but later drops due to malaria endemic in the population while the co-infection trajectories decreases and remain the same.

VI. Conclusion

In this work, a thorough mathematical analysis for a model was conducted to incorporate the biological features of both Ebola virus and malaria disease. The analysis showed that the model is well-posed, the disease free equilibria for the model was obtained and basic reproduction number $R_{EM} = 0.8607599873$ of the Ebola-malaria co-infection model is calculated. The models were analyzed for stability and it was established that the disease free equilibrium of each model and their co-infections were locally and globally asymptotically stable whenever the basic reproduction number is less than unity or endemic otherwise. Sensitivity analysis on the basic reproduction number in table 3 and the graph in figure 6 shows that by eliminating the co-infection contact rate of Ebola- malaria disease in the population in order to control Ebola-malaria co-infection.

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